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Leveraging AI-Driven Accounting for Sustainable Safety of Critical Infrastructure Projects

Kenneth O. Ogirri

Senior Project Scheduler, American Electrical Power - Tulsa, Oklahoma, kennywallz@yahoo.com

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly optimizing and revolutionizing various spheres of life. Its presence in and impact on accounting and project management is well known. This study avers that AI-driven accounting optimizes and revolutionizes the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects. To prove this stance, data are drawn from survey questionnaire, observation, introspection, and library and internet print materials for evidence. Survey design and mixed method alongside their associated plausible descriptive and statistical tools are employed. The results of the analysis show majority of the respondents, and extant studies confirming that AI-driven accounting allows for the integration of the cutting edge technologies into accounting activities; efficient scenario planning and supportive decision-making; automated and optimized sustainability metrics and reporting; predictive analysis and automated management of risks; and transparent stakeholder engagement; improved analysis and reporting of data; automation of regulation and reporting. The study concludes that AI-driven accounting increases the contributions of accounting to the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects to a large extent. Stakeholders are charged to ensure increased adoption of AI

techniques for accounting and project management, towards attaining sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects.

Keywords: AI-driven accounting, Sustainable safety, Critical infrastructure projects, Optimization, Automation

Introduction

The functioning of most systems and sectors of society depends on critical infrastructure (Akinola, 2024; Okusi, 2024). Putting critical infrastructure in place begins with the project phase. That is why this study considers the sustainable safety critical infrastructure projects as what should be given utmost priority. Infrastructure refers to the vital physical and organizational structures and facilities needed, relied on, and used by nations, organizations and individuals for various activities, which include buildings, electricity, power line supplies, schools, roads, water supply, transportation, telecommunications, and healthcare resources (Binhammad et al., 2024; Yu, 2024). Different projects are carried out in each of the spheres of critical infrastructure. The failure to maintain the assets in various systems and spheres results in malfunctioning, damages, disruptions, and financial losses (Odunayo, 2024; Olejnik et al., 2020). As such, the need for AI-driven accounting to attain the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure (projects) cannot be overemphasized. The crucial role played by accounting and artificial intelligence cannot be underestimated.

Since AI-driven reactive, preventive, predictive and proactive approaches to the maintenance of critical infrastructure allow for empirical analytics of large data (Zonta et al., 2020), this study proposes AI-driven accounting as a viable measure for attaining the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects. This measure is result-oriented, problem-solving, cost-effective, seamless, timesaving, resource-saving, interventional and risk-proactive. Studies confirm the efficacy of using AI techniques for predicting, reacting to and preventing facility errors, breakdowns, malfunction, disruptions and damages or untold costs (Akinola et al., 2024; Kalnawat et al., 2024; Ojo et al., 2024; Yu, 2024; Pasupuleti, 2023; Shawana, 2022; Nguyen et al., 2022; Zonta et al., 2020). It is to attain the foregoing that this study proposes AI-driven accounting for the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects. The study considers machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), robotics, and natural language processing (NLP) as the major AI techniques for AI-driven accounting and for safeguarding critical infrastructure projects. The study seeks to answer the following questions:

- (i) What constitutes AI-driven accounting?
- (ii) What role does AI play in accounting and critical infrastructure projects?
- (iii) How can AI-driven accounting ensure the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects?

Related Studies

Kalnawat's et al. (2024) study demonstrates the capacity of machine learning in safeguarding infrastructure from cyber threats. It calls on stakeholders to increase the utilization of machine learning techniques for solutions to various problems requiring advanced techniques for solution. Apart from machine learning, other AI models are proven to be capable of addressing different arching issues in various spheres, including those confronting critical infrastructure as well as critical infrastructure projects. Similarly, Thapaliya and Bokani, (2024) show that machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing are AI techniques that can adequately tackle cyber security threats; identify the patterns of malicious activities in comparison with the legitimate ones; empower security systems with large data in real-time; and automate incident response processes that allow for proactive actions and efficient quelling of risks. Their study provides a scholarly backing to the present study, though it does not take up the same thematic concerns with the present study.

Ojo et al. (2024) find out that blockchain, internet of things (IoT) and autonomous technologies can improve the resilience of critical systems. This means that AI technologies can optimize and automate critical infrastructure as well as the sustainable safety and the accounting activities of critical infrastructure projects. In the same vein, Volk (2024) demonstrates that AI techniques can detect and prevent risks to critical infrastructure and many other systems. The study emphasizes the need to significantly integrate AI technologies into critical infrastructure in order to ensure maximal safety, and optimal operations and functioning. Also, the National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence Bangladesh [NSAIB] (2020) states that AI technologies have the capability to protect critical infrastructure and improve the associated services.

Okusi's (2024) study proves that AI and machine learning have the capacity to detect, predict, resist and prevent threats to critical infrastructure; optimize the safety of critical infrastructure through automated and effective management of risks; create high level of awareness about how to optimally maintain critical infrastructure; and simulate and train human employees in the industry. It concludes that AI and machine learning have more capacities and opportunities for safeguarding critical infrastructure from risks than the other mechanisms, emphasizing the imperative of adopting AI and machine learning for safeguarding critical infrastructure. The present study argues that if AI techniques could do so, they can also automate, optimize and safeguard accounting activities and critical infrastructure projects.

Thuraka et al. (2024) discuss the place of AI and strategic management in the success of various critical projects. The study proposes the combination of the two sets of strategies for the attainment of successes in project planning, execution, maintenance and sustenance. The analysis of the various secondary data gathered for the study reveals that AI and strategic management play multifaceted functions in projects and can foster the success of national and international critical infrastructure projects, once deployed judiciously. Thus, the study determines the efficacy of both AI techniques

and strategic management strategies. The implication is that the combined integration of AI and strategic management into the critical infrastructure projects can undoubtedly yield huge positive results.

Wiese's (2024) study demonstrates that predictive techniques of artificial intelligence can help in the maintenance of critical infrastructure. It emphasizes that critical infrastructure are essential to various sectors, including water resource management, telecommunications, transportation, and energy. They have safety and economic values in no measurable ways. Given their importance, optimizing them by using AI predictive maintenance techniques can prevent failures and risks. The study concludes that AI-driven predictive maintenance of critical infrastructure can present a framework for reliable decision-making on how best to address technical challenges, ensure regulatory compliance, and impact the economy of society. The study undoubtedly relates to the present one. It captures the critical infrastructure aspect of the present study. However, it is not concerned with the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects and AI-driven accounting in the maintenance of critical infrastructure projects. The present study covers these other unexplored concerns, thereby bridging several research gaps.

Zhang et al. (2019) prove that machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) allow for accuracy and efficiency. For example, random forests and support vector machines are ML models for predictive maintenance. Predictive maintenance is the practice of using real-time data and historical records to predict possible equipment failure and proffer remedy before time (Carvalho et al., 2019). While traditional predictive maintenance relies on fixed schedules, AI-driven predictive maintenance seamlessly, timely and proactively examines, predicts and detects the conditions of assets without waiting until the fixed schedules. By so doing, they prevent failures, breakdowns, unnecessary interventions and the possible effects of failures on safety and service delivery.

Indeed, ML models, such as the aforementioned, have the capacity to process large amounts of data, with which they identify patterns and looming equipment failures (Schwabacher & Goebel, 2007). These cannot be done by traditional systems. Also, neural networks, which are models of DL, can capture more complex failure modes. The ability to capture complex failures make them more effective in handling large volumes of datasets in any sectors of critical infrastructure, such as energy, telecommunication, water management and architecture (Pasupuleti et al., 2024; Ren et al., 2021).

In their study of 70 project managers involved in eco-friendly building projects, Tabassi et al. (2016) show that the leadership style of project managers influences the way they handle projects. There is no doubt that the projects handled by the project management professionals have different economic benefits and impact on the economy of every nation. The study further shows that good leadership and personality attributes are needed for sustainable achievement and building of any projects. While the present study agrees with theirs, it goes on to propose the utilization of AI-driven accounting as a mechanism for project success, the safety of projects and their associated critical infrastructure, and

the sustenance of both projects and critical infrastructure. For the present study, additional to managerial and intellectual competencies, the integration of AI techniques into the project phases of critical infrastructure can guarantee significant eco-friendly building projects. The integration can also optimize and revolutionize managerial and intellectual competencies. The focus of the present study is on automated and optimized accounting for the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects.

Salako (2023) demonstrates that the implementation of technology-based strategies guarantees huge results in the construction sector. It is in consideration of effective management construction projects that this study advocates AI-driven accounting for the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects. Of course, there is no doubt that when the accounting phase of critical infrastructure projects gets automated and optimized, more positive results would be attained. The results would include effective management of time, costs and resources, accountability, accuracy, transparency, effective budgeting and scheduling, effective communication and stakeholder collaboration, adequate savings and financial security, and detection, prediction and prevention of faults, malfunction and risks (Akinloye et al., 2024).

Methodology

Survey design and mixed method are employed. These are chosen based on the nature and preoccupation of the study. The design allows for a survey of the thematic concerns online, using Google Form for collection of questionnaire data. Upon posting the online questionnaire on two WhatsApp group platforms, the researcher pleaded with members to help fill the questionnaire anonymously. The groups house professionals in accounting and critical infrastructure. Some of them are lecturers/instructors, students of advanced degrees, and expertise consultants of international repute.

In one of the groups, 29 members filled the form within 4 days, with no other members filling further. After 5 days of no further response to the questionnaire, the researcher informed the group that the limit had been reached. So, if there were other intending respondents, they should no longer bother about filling the questionnaire. Within these days, 31 questionnaires were filled by some members of the other group. Again, the researcher announced an end to the filling of the posted online questionnaire.

For equal representation and equitable distribution, the last 2 filled questionnaires on the other group were not included in the 29 realized before the 2 were filled. At last, 58 respondents were involved in the online questionnaire. The responses are synthesized, interpreted, described, presented and analyzed both statistically and descriptively. The following answer options are included in the online questionnaire Google Form: Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Neutral (N), Strongly Disagreed (SD), and Disagreed (D). These are abbreviated in tables viz: SA, A, N, SD and D.

Additional to the online questionnaire, observation and introspection were relied on for supplementary primary data. By these, the researcher sourced data from participant and non-participant observations and his professional experiences, experiential learning, and acquired educational knowledge of AI, accounting, project management, safety and critical infrastructure. More so, secondary data were relied on extensively. These include journals, textbooks, theses, and several categories of academic and conventional papers. These data sources were drawn from the internet and the library. Analytic description and content and thematic analyses were employed for the secondary data.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1

Constituents of AI-driven accounting and critical infrastructure projects

S/N	Variables	SA	A	N	SD	D
AI-driven accounting and critical infrastructure comprise the following						
AI-driven accounting	Machine learning algorithms (e.g. decision support systems) Deep learning algorithms Connecting with financial software Advanced analytics and reporting Cloud computing Robotic process Natural language processing Data entry automation Automation Security and data User interface and experience Continuous learning and improvement Risk management and compliance	19 (32.8%)	39 (67.2%)	-	-	-
Critical infrastructure projects	Renewable energy production pipelines, plants and plant treatment, pump usage and leakages in the energy sector Transportation (roads, railways, airlines and aircrafts, waterways and ships, boats, etc.) Water management Hardware and software systems in the telecommunication sector	43 (74.1%)	15 (25.9%)	-	-	-

	Healthcare systems and resources					
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Source, Author, 2025

What constitute AI-driven accounting and critical infrastructure projects are listed in the Table 1 and proven by all the 58 respondents. None of them disagreed to the identified components of AI-driven accounting and critical infrastructure projects respectively. The identified constituents of AI-driven accounting are affirmed by 19 (32.8%) respondents, agreed strongly, and 39 (67.2%), who agreed but strongly. Besides, the identified components of critical infrastructure projects confirmed by 43 (74.1%), who agreed strongly, and 15 (25.9%), who agreed but not strongly. The identified components aptly and symbolically describe AI-driven accounting and critical infrastructure projects. The figure 2 provided below summarizes AI-driven accounting as a pathway to sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects:

Figure 1

Components of AI-Driven Accounting

Source: Author, 2025

Table 2

Roles of AI in accounting and critical infrastructure projects

S/N	Variables	SA	A	N	SD	D
The following are common roles or benefits of AI in accounting and critical infrastructure projects						
1	Automation, optimization, innovations, inventions and discoveries	7 (12.1%)	-	-	-	-

	Offering appreciable level of accounting accuracy, accountability and financial safety Fostering effective planning, scheduling Enhancing performance, operations, and service delivery Providing and managing large data Ensuring data-driven decision-making					
2	Preventing delays Reducing costs, and time and resource wastages Predictions and detections Compliance management Incident reporting and response Fostering environmental sustainability	5 (8.6%)		-	-	-
3	All of the above	46 (79.3%)	-	-	-	-
4	None of the above	-	-	-	-	-

Source: Author, 2025

Given the affirmed roles or benefits, there is no gainsaying the fact that AI-driven accounting can greatly impact accounting and the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects. The main roles, which constitute the major benefits, are upheld by all the respondents. The respondents are of different sets. Interestingly, all the three sets of respondents opted for the “Strongly Agreed” in choosing each of the variables they did. Thus, 46 (79.3%) chose the Variable 3 “All of the above”, which means that they chose Variables 1 and 2 combined; 7 respondents, representing 12.1%, chose Variable 1; while the other 5 respondents of 8.6% chose Variable 2.

Table 3

AI-driven accounting in ensuring the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects

S/N	Variables	SA	A	N	SD	D
How AI-driven accounting can ensure the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects						
1	Through identification and prediction functions, as in detection, automation, and accuracy of actions against cyber threats, and optimization and response to risks and faults AI-driven models are capable of organizing the networks for, and strengthening the functions of infrastructure AI to proffer solutions through detection and prompt response to cyber threats to energy infrastructure	10 (17.3%)	-	-	-	-

	Human actions against cyber threats get enhanced and optimized by AI Cyber attacks on water and transport infrastructure can be foiled by AI technologies, if adopted and used appropriately ML can optimize workflows and resources, thereby enabling the realization of sustainable development goals					
2	ML optimizes human interpretable decisions on security automation and intelligence for the protection of critical infrastructure projects Facilitating efficient maintenance of critical infrastructure, including saving costs of maintaining infrastructure in the energy sector, particularly as they accurately predict failures and extend the lifespan of equipment Detection of and response to threats With AI and ML, the level of awareness about real-time situations gets increased Simulation and training, including simulation of knowledge gaps Efficient assessment and management of risks	-	7 (12.1%)	-	-	-
3	All of the above	41 (70.6)	-	-	-	-
4	None of the above	-	-	-	-	-

Source: Author, 2025

On how AI-driven accounting can ensure the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects, 10 (17.3%) agreed strongly to the study's identified ways through which AI-driven accounting can do that in Variable 1. Next, 7 (12.1%) agreed but not strongly to the items listed in Variable 2. The largest ratio of responses obtained in response to the Research Question 3 is 41 (70.6) for "Strongly Agreed". In all, the responses show that AI-driven can ensure the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects.

Table 4

Challenges to AI-driven accounting and the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects

S/N	Variables	SA	A	N	SD	D
The major challenges to AI-driven accounting and the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects include						

1	Technicalities of AI and technical issues, data availability and quality, computational resources and their shortages	-	7 (12.1%)	-	-	-
2	High costs, tasking schedules, savings inadequacies, regulatory embargoes and violations of established standards, policy and research gaps, the cumbersome nature of AI models and their exhibition of bias	10 (17.3%)	-	-	-	-
3	All of the above	41 (70.6)	-	-	-	-
4	None of the above	-	-	-	-	-

Source: Author, 2025

Obviously, all the respondents strongly agreed that the identified factors constitute the major challenges to AI-driven accounting and the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects. Although all of them affirmed the listed challenges, 7 of 12.1% “agreed” to the Variable 1; 10 of 17.3% “strongly agreed” to the Variable 2; and 41 of 70.6% “strongly agreed” to the Variable 3. No response was obtained for the Variable 4. On the whole, all the respondents confirmed that the listed factors are challenges to AI-driven accounting and the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects.

Conclusion

From all indications, it is quite clear that AI-driven accounting can ensure the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects. This study has shown that AI-driven accounting optimizes and revolutionizes the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects. Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly optimizing and revolutionizing various spheres of life. Its presence in and impact on accounting and project management is affirmed in the literature. Ultimately, with predictions and intelligible insights into the safety of critical infrastructure, there is reliability in the accounting data for the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects.

AI-driven accounting allows for the integration of machine learning, internet of things and other AI techniques and smart technologies; efficient scenario planning and supportive decision-making; automated and optimized sustainability metrics and reporting; predictive analysis and automated management of risks; transparent stakeholder engagement; improved analysis and reporting of data; automation of regulation and reporting. Therefore, AI-driven accounting increases the contributions of accounting to the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects to a large extent. Stakeholders are charged to ensure increased adoption of AI techniques for accounting and project management, so as to ensure the sustainable safety of critical infrastructure projects.

References

- Akinloye, A., Anwansedo, S., & Akinwande, O. T. (2024). AI-driven threat detection and response systems for secure national infrastructure networks: a comprehensive review. *International Journal of Latest Technology in Engineering, Management & Applied Science (IJLTEMAS)*, XIII (VII), 82-92. DOI: 10.51583/IJLTEMAS
- Akinola, A. P. (2024). Leveraging cost-effective AI and smart technologies for rapid infrastructural development in USA. *African Journal of Advances in Science and Technology Research*, 15(1), 59-71. <https://doi.org/10.62154/rktd4f30>
- Akinola, A. P., Thuraka, B., & Okpeseyi, S. B. A. (2024). Achieving housing affordability in the U.S. through sustained use of AI and robotic process automation for prefabricated modular construction. *African Journal of Advances in Science and Technology Research*, 15(1), 122-134. <https://doi.org/10.62154/53t99n63>
- Binhammad, M., Alqaydi, S., Othman, A., & Abuljadayel, L. H. (2024). The role of AI in cyber security: Safeguarding digital identity. *Journal of Information Security*, 15, 245-278. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jis.2024.152015>
- Carvalho, T. P., et al. (2019). A review of machine learning and Internet of Things (IoT) in smart maintenance. *Computers in Industry*, 107, 100-117.
- Kalnawat, A., Dhabliya, D., Vydehi, K., Dhabliya, A., & Kumar, S. D. (2024). Safeguarding critical infrastructures: Machine learning in cybersecurity. *(ICECS'24) E3S Web of Conferences*, 491, 02025. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202449102025>
- Na, J., et al. (2020). Predictive maintenance for water management using artificial intelligence: A systematic review. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 258, 110038.
- National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence Bangladesh (2020). *Information and communication technology division government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh*.
- Odunayo, A. (2024). Leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) for the maintenance of science laboratory equipment. *African Journal of Advances in Science and Technology Research*, 16(1), 131-148. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.62154/ajastr.2024.016.010453>
- Ojo, B., Ogborigbo, J. C., & Okafor, M. O. (2024). Innovative solutions for critical infrastructure resilience against cyber-physical attacks. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 22(03), 1651-1674. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.22.3.1921>
- Okusi, O. (2024). Leveraging AI and machine learning for the protection of critical national infrastructure. *Asian Journal of Research in Computer Science*, 17(10), 1-11, no.AJRCOS.124252. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajrcos/2024/v17i10505>

- Olejnik, S., et al. (2020). The importance of AI-based maintenance in critical infrastructure. *Sustainability*, 12(23), 10092.
- Pasupuleti, V. (2023, Dec.). Ascertaining the extent to which AI is revolutionizing architecture: Exploratory survey. *Journal of Innovations in Engineering & Tech. Res. (JIETR2023)*, 2(2), 65-77.
- Pasupuleti, V., Kodete, C. S., Thuraka, B., & Sangaraju, V. V. (2024). Impact of AI on architecture: An exploratory thematic analysis. *African Journal of Advances in Science and Technology Research*, 16(1), 117-130. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.62154/ajastr.2024.016.010453>
- Rashid A. B., Ashfakul, K. K., Hassan, A., & Mehedy, H. B. (2023). Artificial intelligence in the military: an overview of the capabilities, applications, and challenges. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*, 2023, 1-31. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/8676366>
- Ren, X., et al. (2021). Predictive maintenance using deep learning: A case study in wind energy. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 17(8), 5486-5495.
- Salako, B. A. (2023). Strategies for implementation of construction management planning tools for effective project delivery in Abuja, Nigeria. Mtech thesis submitted to the Postgraduate School, Federal University of Technology, Minna, Nigeria.
- Schwabacher, M., & Goebel, K. (2007). A survey of artificial intelligence for prognostics. AAAI Fall Symposium: AI for Prognostics, 1-8.
- Shawana, T. A. (2022). Carbon emissions as threats to environmental sustainability: Exploring conventional and technology-based remedies. *African Journal of Environmental Sciences and Renewable Energy*, 8 (1). <https://publications.afropolitanjournals.com/index.php/ajesre/article/view/736>
- Tabassi, A. A., Argyropoulou, M., Roufechaei, K. M. & Argyropoulou, R. (2016). Leadership behavior of project managers in sustainable construction projects. *Procedia Computer Science*, 100, 724-730.
- Thapaliya, S., & Bokani, A. (2024). Leveraging artificial intelligence for enhanced cybersecurity: Insights and innovations. *Sadgamaya*, vol.1, iss.1, 46-53.
- Thuraka, B., Pasupuleti, V., Malisetty, S., & Ogirri, K. O. (2024). Leveraging artificial intelligence and strategic management for success in inter/national projects in US and beyond. *Journal of Engineering Research and Reports*, 26 (8), 49-59. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jerr/2024/v26i81228>.
- Volk, M. (2024). A safer future: Leveraging the AI power to improve the cybersecurity in critical infrastructures. *ELEKTROTEHNIŠKI VESTNIK*, 91(3), 73-94.

- Wiese, T. L. (2024). Predictive maintenance using artificial intelligence in critical infrastructure: A decision-making framework. *International Journal of Engineering, Business and Management (IJEEM)*, 8(4), 1-4. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.22161/ijebm.8.4.1>
- Yu, C. (2024). "AI as critical infrastructure: Safeguarding national security in the age of artificial intelligence," Preprint, pp. 1-16. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/u4kdg>
- Zhang, Q., et al. (2019). Deep learning for predictive maintenance of industrial equipment: A review. *IEEE Access*, 7, 62624-62634.
- Zonta, T., et al. (2020). Predictive maintenance in the Industry 4.0: A systematic literature review. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 150, 106889.